

Ficha de Personagem		
Nome		
Papel		
Atributos (Distribua 18 pontos ao longo de todos os atributos)		
Soft Skills: ○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○ ○○○○○○	Hard Skills: ○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○ ○○○○○○	Domínio do escopo: ○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○○ ○○○○○○
Experiência: ○○○○○○	Experiência: ○○○○○○	Experiência: ○○○○○○

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Experiência: ○○○○○○	Experiência: ○○○○○○	Experiência: ○○○○○○

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Experiência: ○○○○○○	Experiência: ○○○○○○	Experiência: ○○○○○○